

Growth Of Digital Payment System and Indian Economy

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Abstract

The year-wise growth in the value of total digital payments during the period 2019-20 to 2023-24 is Rs.. 1,61,9,68,680 crore in the FY 2019-20. Considering the value growth in digital transactions based 2019-20, it has decreased by 12.66% in 2020-21. This is because this was the period of COVID-19, during which the economy had a huge decline in credit transactions. The highest record growth in digital value is seen in the FY 2021-22 at 23.28%. Whereas, in the FY 2022-23, 2023-24, a growth of 19.66% and 16.35% has been seen, respectively. Similarly, the total volume of digital transactions was Rs. 340156 lakh in 2019-20. On that basis, when the annual growth in the volume of transactions is taken into account, it is seen that the highest growth of 64.68% occurred in the FY 2021-22 in these five years. While the lowest annual growth of 28.49% occurred in the year 2020-21

Notably, the total UPI transaction value was about 86% of India's GDP in FY 2022. This figure shows the growing popularity and acceptance of UPI as a convenient and secure platform for digital transactions in India. Currently, there are 350 million active UPI users in India and 340 million QR codes at various merchant locations to enable seamless digital payments. The UPI ecosystem is vast, with over 77 mobile applications including players like Google Pay, WhatsApp, Amazon Pay, PhonePe (Walmart-backed), and BHIM. According to ACI's 2024 Global Report, India accounted for about 49% of the world's instant payment transactions in digital transactions in 2023. India has also surpassed China in terms of digital payments. Digital transactions in India have reached 89.5 million. India is followed by Brazil with 29.2 million, China with 17.6 million, Thailand with 16.5 million, and South Korea with 8 million. These countries were once ahead of India in terms of digital payments.

Keyword: Digital payment, average, growth rate, transaction value, volume, Indian economy,

INTRODUCTION:

In recent times, we have witnessed a kind of digital revolution in the Indian economy. Citizens have become more aware of digital payment methods, which have

Received: 5 May 2025

Revised: 9 May 2025

Accepted: 12 May 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15395095](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15395095)

accelerated financial transactions and improved living standards. But the foundation for this was laid four decades ago in the form of financial reforms. The Central Bank issued the first Indian bank credit card in 1980. A few years later, in 1987, HSBC installed the first ATM in Mumbai. Then in the 1990s, debit card facilities were introduced and ATMs became more common. In the 2000s, internet banking became more popular and people started shopping online, making it easier for them to do online banking. In 2003, Buildex launched one of its offerings as a payment aggregator for merchants, while in 2004, the first e-wallet called Oxygen Wallet was launched. In 2005, the National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) was established, managed and maintained by the Institute for Development and Research in Banking Technology. Later, in 2010, IMPS was publicly launched in Mumbai. In the 2010s, mobile banking apps became very popular and smart phones started using them more widely. In 2012, the RuPay card scheme was developed by the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI).

In the Union Budget 2017-18, the government had set a target of 2,500 crore digital transactions through UPI, USSD, Aadhaar Pay, IMPS and debit cards to further promote digital payment transactions in the country. Accordingly, the government has significantly increased the use of digital payment methods such as mobile wallets, UPI, and card payments to increase the use of digital payments and reduce dependence on cash transactions. However, a large section of the population still relies on cash transactions, and to reduce that dependence, it is encouraging the use of digital payments, including subsidies for merchants to purchase point-of-sale terminals and tax incentives for businesses that accept digital payment methods.

The Government of India is actively promoting the use of digital technology through various initiatives such as Digital India, Make in India, and Startup India. These initiatives aim to increase the use of digital technology in various sectors such as healthcare, education and agriculture to create a conducive environment for start-ups to flourish.

India has seen a significant growth in digital payment transactions in recent times since the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) launched UPI in 2016, which allows real-time inter-bank transactions, and the Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) app, which simplifies the process of making digital transactions. E-RUPI, a cashless and

contactless instrument for digital payments in 2021, The pandemic accelerated the adoption of digital payments in the 2020s. Contactless payments became more widely available and convenient. India has several electronic payment systems, including UPI, NEFT, RTGS, IMPS, and AEPS.

The demonetization policy in India had a significant impact on the Indian economy, which accelerated the growth of digital payments in India. Before demonetization, digital payments accounted for only 10% of all transactions in India, but since then, this number has increased to more than 20%. This policy move has actually led to public awareness and promotion of digital transactions in India. The rise in internet and smart phone usage in India has also played a major role in the growth of the digital transaction in economy. This growth in internet users has also led to an increase in the number of mobile wallet users in India, which is expected to reach 900 million by 2025. Apart from this, the number of credit card users in the country has doubled in the last five years and has reached Rs 10.80 crore. The number of debit cards has increased from 80.53 crore in December 2019 to 99.09 crore by December 2024.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the various digital payment systems and its transaction growth of the Indian economy.
2. To study the year-wise growth of digital transactions in the Indian economy.
3. To know the impacts of digital transactions of users and the Government.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

To investigate the impact of the digital payment system on the Indian economy, a multifaceted research methodology would be crucial. Growth of digital payments in India as well as growth of selected categories during the five FY from 2019-2020 to 2023-2024. To analyse the growth performance during the period under study, both volume and value of transactions of five different digital payment methods, namely, RTGS, Debit Transfers and Direct Debits, Prepaid Payment Instruments, Credit Transfer, and Card Payment.

Secondary data for the period under study has been collected from reports published by the Reserve Bank of India, research papers and various articles and newspapers. Analysis

for result the utilization of statistical tools like, Mean, Annual Growth Rate (AGR), and graphs as well.

DIGITAL PAYMENT METHODS IN INDIA:

In India, various digital payment methods have become popular, which has radically changed the financial transactions of the country. Some of the major digital payment methods are as follows:

1. **Unified Payments Interface (UPI):** UPI allows instant money transfer between bank accounts using a mobile platform. It has gained massive traction due to its easy-to-use and interoperability across various banks and apps.
2. **Mobile Wallets:** Services like Paytm, PhonePe, Google Pay, and others offer mobile wallet solutions. Users can store money digitally and make payments for various services and goods.
3. **Debit/Credit Cards:** Traditional card payments using debit or credit cards are prevalent, both online and at physical POS terminals.
4. **Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM):** This is a government-backed UPI app that facilitates simple, quick, and secure transactions using UPI.
5. **Aadhaar Enabled Payment System (AEPS):** AEPS enables transactions using Aadhaar authentication, allowing individuals to make payments or withdrawals using their biometric information.
6. **Bank Prepaid Cards:** Banks issue prepaid cards that users can load with funds and use for online transactions or at POS terminals.
7. **National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) And Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS):** These are electronic fund transfer systems used for larger transactions between banks, operated by the Reserve Bank of India.
8. **Immediate Payment Service (IMPS):** IMPS allows real-time inter-bank electronic fund transfer through mobile phones. These methods collectively offer a wide range of choices for consumers and businesses to conduct digital transactions conveniently and securely in India.

DIGITAL PAYMENT GROWTH AND INDIAN ECONOMY:

Received: 5 May 2025

Revised: 9 May 2025

Accepted: 12 May 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15395095](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15395095)

The data released by the Reserve Bank of India shows that digital payments in the country have increased by 11.11 percent on an annual basis. In September 2024, the digital payment index reached 465.33, while in March 2024 it was 445.5. This increase in the index is seen in six months.

The transaction value and volume of various instruments used for digital transactions are shown year-wise. The total value of transactions made digitally in the Indian economy during the five years from 2019-20 to 2023-24 is Rs. 929337073 crore and the volume is Rs. 4280675 lakh, The annual growth rate is also shown in Table No. 1 and 2 below.

Table No: 1 Year wise Value of Payment Settlement System

(Value in Rs. Cr)

Sr. No	Payment Settlement Systems	2019-20		2020-21		2021-22		2022-23		2023-24		Average Value
		Value	AG R	Value	AG R	Value	AG R	Value	AG R	Value	AG R	
1	Large Value Credit Transfers - RTGS	131156475	0	105599849	-19.48	128657516	21.83	149946286	16.55	170886670	13.96	549537460
2	2. Credit Transfers	28556593	0	33504226	17.32	42728006	27.53	55009620	28.74	67542859	22.78	173307017
3	3. Debit Transfers and Direct Debits	605939	0	865520	42.83	1034444	19.52	1289611	24.67	1687658	30.86	4133045.6
4	4. Card Payments	1434813	0	1291799	-9.96	1701851	31.74	2152245	26.45	2423563	12.60	7065420.6
5	5. Prepaid Payment Instruments	214860	0	197095	-8.26	279416	41.76	287111	2.75	283048	-1.41	1035091.6
Total Digital Payments		161968680	0	141458489	-12.66	174401233	23.28	208684873	19.66	242823798	16.35	735078035

Source: Reserve Bank of India report-2025

Table No: 2 Year wise Volume of Payment Settlement System

(Volume in Lakh)

Sr. No.	Payment Settlement Systems	2019-20		2020-21		2021-22		2022-23		2023-24		Average Volume
		Volume	AGR	Volume	AGR	Volume	AGR	Volume	AGR	Volume	AGR	
1	Large Value Credit Transfers - RTGS	1507	0	1592	5.64	2078	30.53	2426	16.75	2700	11.29	2060.6
2	Credit Transfers	206297	0	317868	35.09	577935	81.82	983621	70.19	1486107	51.08	714365.6
3	Debit Transfers and Direct Debits	6027	0	10457	42.36	12189	16.56	15343	25.87	18250	18.94	12453.2
4	Card Payments	72384	0	57787	20.16	61783	6.915	63325	2.49	58470	-7.67	62749.8
5	Prepaid Payment Instruments	53941	0	49366	-8.48	65783	33.25	74667	13.50	78775	5.50	64506.4
Total Digital Payments		340156	0	437070	28.49	719768	64.68	1139382	58.29	1644302	44.31	856135.6

Source: Reserve Bank of India-report 2025.

Received: 5 May 2025

Revised: 9 May 2025

Accepted: 12 May 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15395095>

Source: RBI Report -2025

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The year-wise growth in the value of total digital payments during the period 2019-20 to 2023-24 is Rs 161968680 crore in the FY 2019-20. Considering the value growth in digital transactions based on this year, it has decreased by 12.66% in 2020-21. This is because this was the period of COVID-19, during which there was a huge decline in credit transactions in the economy. The highest record growth in digital value is seen in the FY 2021-22 at 23.28%. Whereas, in the FY 2022-23, 2023-24, a growth of 19.66% and 16.35% has been seen in digital transactions, respectively. Similarly, the total volume of digital transactions was Rs 340156 lakh in 2019-20. On that basis, when the annual growth in the volume of transactions is taken into account, it is seen that the highest growth of 64.68% occurred in the FY 2021-22 out of these five years. While the lowest annual growth of 28.49% occurred in the year 2020-21, as can be seen from the above table.

When considering the average value of major digital instruments in the five years the highest average value of Rs. 549537460 crore is for the RTGS instrument. The lowest average value of Rs. 1035091.6 crore is for prepaid auto pay payment instruments. When considering the average number of digital transactions, the highest number of transactions are for credit transfer instrument at Rs. 714365.6 lakh, while the lowest number is for the RTGS instrument at Rs 2060.60 lakh.

Considering the year-wise growth of instruments used for digital transactions, in the FY 2019-20, the transaction value of RTGS instrument is the highest at Rs. 131156475 crore among the total digital transaction values. The lowest value is that of auto pay prepaid payment

instruments at Rs.214860 crore. Based on this value, if we consider the value growth rate of the FY 2020-21, the highest growth rate of 42.83% is that of the Debit Transfer and Direct Debits instrument. The lowest negative growth rate of 19.48% is that of the RTGS instrument. In the FY 2021-22, the highest annual growth of 41.76% in the value of digital transactions has been achieved through auto-pay prepaid payment instruments. While the annual growth of 19.52% has been seen in debit transfer and direct debit instruments. Similarly, in 2022-23, the growth in digital value has changed and the highest growth of 28.74% has been seen in credit transfer. The lowest growth of 2.75% has been achieved in prepaid payment instruments. In the FY 2023-24, the highest growth of 30.86% in digital value has been achieved through debit transfer and direct debit instruments. While the lowest negative growth of 1.41% has also been achieved in prepaid payment instruments.

When considering the transaction volume of various instruments used for digital transactions year-wise, the highest volume of Rs.72384 lakhs was recorded by the credit payment instrument in the FY 2019-20, and the lowest volume of Rs.1507 lakhs was recorded by the RTGS instrument. When considering the volume growth rate based on the FY 2019-20, the highest growth of 42.36% in 2020-21 is seen in debit transfer and direct debit. While the negative volume growth of 8.48% is seen in the RTGS instrument. In the FY 2021-22, the highest volume growth of 81.82% is seen in credit transfer instrument, and the lowest volume growth of 6.91% is seen in the prepaid payment instrument. Similarly, in the year 2022-23, the highest volume growth of 70.19 percent has been in credit transfer while the lowest volume growth of 2.49% has been in credit payment. In the financial year 2023-24, the highest volume growth of 51.08% has been in credit transfer and the lowest volume growth of 7.67% has been in credit payment instrument.

IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY:

1. The Government Benefits From the Digital Economy

The government benefits from the digital economy in several ways:

1. Administrative costs are reduced. The digitization process has resulted in savings in printing, storage, and manpower costs of documents.

2. Tax revenue increases for the government: Digital transactions make it easier for the government to track financial activities and improve tax compliance.
3. Efficient service delivery: Digital platforms enable the government to ensure that public welfare schemes, subsidies, etc. directly reach the intended beneficiaries and it also ensures that the benefits of services are delivered.
4. Data-driven decision-making: The digital economy generates a large amount of data. The government can use this data to make informed policy decisions, optimize resource allocation and enhance governance.
5. Promotion of Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Digital transactions promote innovation and entrepreneurship, which leads to the growth of new businesses and job creation. This creates a positive impact on economic growth. Overall, the government benefits from technological advancements.
6. Enhanced Economic Growth: The digital economy contributes to overall economic growth by attracting more investment, creating new industries in the country, expanding the economy and creating new employment opportunities in various sectors.
7. Improves the quality of life of the citizens: Digital platforms enable the government to deliver better public services like healthcare, education and infrastructure. This improves the quality of life of citizens and has a positive impact on the economy.
8. Better governance: Digital tools provide governments with real-time data analysis, which helps in decision-making and policy formulation.
9. Transparency and accountability in economic transactions: Digital systems creates transparent records and audit trails, reduce corruption and increase accountability in government operations. This transparency increases public trust in the administration and it achieve the overall socio-economic development.

2. Users Benefits From Digital Economy:

1. **Convenience:** Digital transactions allow users to make payments or conduct financial activities anytime, anywhere, as long as they have access to a digital device and an internet connection. This eliminates the need to visit physical banks or carry cash, making it incredibly convenient for both buyers and sellers.

2. **Enhanced Security:** Digital transactions utilize encryption technology, secure payment gateways and stringent security measures to protect sensitive financial information. This reduces the risk of fraud, unauthorized access, and identity theft, providing users with peace of mind.
3. **Speed and Efficiency:** Compared to traditional payment methods, digital transactions are significantly faster and more efficient. Payments are processed almost instantly, eliminating the need for manual processing or physical paperwork.
4. **Streamlined Record keeping:** Digital transactions generate electronic records, making it easy to track and manage financial activities. Users can access transaction history, receipts, and other financial documents digitally, simplifying record keeping and eliminating the need for physical storage space.
5. **Reduced Costs:** Digital transactions often entail lower transaction fees compared to traditional payment methods. This cost-effectiveness benefits both individuals and businesses, allowing them to save on expenses associated with cash handling, manual processing, and transportation.

CONCLUSION:

When considering different payment methods in the total digital payment transfer value, credit transfer has seen the highest growth in every year from 2019-20 to 2023-24. While the lowest growth has been in AEPS fund transfer payment method. Also, when considering the volume growth of digital payment, UPI payment method has seen the most change. It is seen that it increases continuously while AEPS fund transfer payment method has seen the lowest volume. Governments and users benefit from the digital economy through improved efficiency, transparency, governance, reduced costs, economic growth, and inclusiveness, leading to better services, enhanced security and a more empowered citizenry. In conclusion, digital transactions have revolutionized the financial landscape, offering individuals and businesses a convenient, secure, and efficient way to manage their finances. Overall, the central government's policy, the Reserve Bank's follow-up, rapidly advancing technology, the increasing number of internet users and smart phone owners, the positive attitude of the public, technology-

oriented start-ups and the significant growth in the size of the e-commerce market, make the future of digital payments in India look very bright.

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